

ASAP KEY RECOMMENDATIONS FOR SCHOOLS, FAMILIES, STAKEHOLDERS & POLICYMAKERS

ASAP KEY RECOMMENDATIONS

**FOR SCHOOLS
AND OTHER
LEARNING
COMMUNITIES**

FOR SCHOOLS AND OTHER LEARNING COMMUNITIES

1. EARLY AND SYSTEMATIC DIGITAL LITERACY IMPLEMENTATION

Recommendation:

Create opportunities within the classroom to implement age-appropriate digital literacy education beginning from first grade, establishing systematic and progressive activities that build skills year over year.

Implementation tips:

- Develop comprehensive, multi-year digital literacy programs with clear learning objectives and assessment methods.
- Address the gap between when children begin using technology and when formal education starts by replacing isolated workshops with continuous learning experiences.
- Establish formative assessment protocols to regularly measure both technical skills and digital citizenship behaviors.

2. PRIORITIZE FOUNDATIONAL SKILLS AND INFORMATION LITERACY

Recommendation:

Emphasize basic digital operations and critical thinking skills before introducing advanced concepts (e.g. programming). Assess your class to integrate a comprehensive understanding of technology's basic principles and ethical dilemmas.

Implementation tips:

- Focus on fundamental skills like document management, password security, email communication, and information verification.
- Teach students to critically analyze online content and verify sources to combat digital misinformation.
- Incorporate real-life scenarios, including scams, cyberbullying consequences, and digital risks, to make learning relatable and impactful.
- Move beyond deficit-based approaches to establish evidence-based foundations for digital literacy education.

FOR SCHOOLS AND OTHER LEARNING COMMUNITIES

3. COMPREHENSIVE RISK AWARENESS AND ONLINE SAFETY

Recommendation:

Address exposure to harmful content while teaching digital footprint awareness and understanding of long-term consequences.

Implementation tips:

- Equip students with skills to recognize and respond to harmful online content, providing clear reporting mechanisms and emotional support resources.
- Build awareness of how online behavior affects future opportunities and relationships, encouraging thoughtful digital participation.
- Address myths, anxieties, and moral panics surrounding digital technology, including oversimplified concerns about stranger danger and screen time limits, to establish evidence-based discussions about digital safety.

4. INTEGRATION OF SOCIAL-EMOTIONAL LEARNING AS A SET OF CORE COMPETENCIES

Recommendation:

Integrate socio-emotional and metacognitive approaches within your classes, to develop self-awareness, emotional regulation, and critical thinking skills alongside technical competencies.

Implementation tips:

- Address shortened attention spans caused by social media consumption through classroom practices and activities that gradually build sustained focus.
- Create explicit connections between digital citizenship and social-emotional learning to counteract declining empathy and strengthen social bonds.
- Recognize and value young people's diverse digital practices beyond entertainment, acknowledging the meaningful role digital platforms play in their social relationships, identity development, and creative expression.

FOR SCHOOLS AND OTHER LEARNING COMMUNITIES

5. INCLUSIVE AND DIFFERENTIATED LEARNING APPROACHES IMPLEMENTATION

Recommendation:

Establish mixed-ability digital literacy groups and address disparities in children's digital experiences and backgrounds through inclusive learning approaches.

Implementation tips:

- Create peer learning opportunities that pair students with varying levels of technological competence to promote mutual support and knowledge exchange.
- Identify the best curricula, activities and materials that meet your classes' needs, expectations, and digital backgrounds, acknowledging that some students may only be familiar with mobile devices while others have broader technological exposure.
- Address motivation, training needs, and time constraints for both students and educators by providing adequate resources, professional development opportunities, and realistic implementation timelines.

6. INTERDISCIPLINARY INTEGRATION AND STUDENT VOICE

Recommendation:

Promote interdisciplinary approaches to digital literacy while amplifying and prioritizing children's voices in discussions and decision-making processes.

Implementation tips:

- Integrate critical analysis and use of technology across subjects, such as exploring algorithms in mathematics classes or examining digital media in language arts.
- Ensure students' perspectives, experiences, and needs are genuinely heard and incorporated into policy and practice.
- Understand the fundamental importance of digital platforms in young people's social lives, recognizing the meaningful connections and communities they create and engage with online.

FOR SCHOOLS AND OTHER LEARNING COMMUNITIES

7. PROMOTION AND ENGAGEMENT IN PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT, AND PEDAGOGICAL INNOVATION INITIATIVES

Recommendation:

Organize regular training initiatives aligned with pre-identified competency gaps and emerging technological developments, while implementing innovative pedagogical tools and resources.

Implementation tips:

- Provide regular, updated training (at least on a yearly basis) for teachers and school staff (administrators, counselors, psychologists and nurses, support staff) on digital literacy and emerging technologies, making opportunities accessible and free to the entire educational community.
- Create teacher collaboration networks to facilitate sharing of best practices and resources. Implement innovative pedagogical approaches including gamification, production-based activities, and collaborative projects that actively engage students.
- Certify educators who complete media literacy training with special professional recognition to incentivize participation and elevate expertise.

8. PARENTS AND FAMILIES ENGAGEMENT

Recommendation:

Develop systematic parent education programs and establish clear communication channels to improve family digital literacy and awareness.

Implementation tips:

- Develop systematic workshops and resources to address the gap where parents lack basic digital knowledge while their children are advanced users, enabling better home supervision and support.
- Create regular communication with parents about digital literacy goals and student progress to build partnerships that reinforce digital citizenship lessons at home and ensure consistent messaging across environments.

FOR SCHOOLS AND OTHER LEARNING COMMUNITIES

9. INTERGENERATIONAL LEARNING INITIATIVES

Recommendation:

Facilitate intergenerational learning activities where students, parents, and grandparents learn together.

Implementation tips:

- Organize events or workshops that allow different generations to share digital knowledge and skills. This bridges generational digital divides while fostering mutual understanding, respect, and solidarity within families and the community, creating a more cohesive approach to digital literacy across age groups.

10. PROMOTION AND ESTABLISHMENT OF MULTI-STAKEHOLDER COLLABORATION AND COMMUNITY PARTNERSHIPS

Recommendation:

Establish multi-stakeholder dialogue and partnerships among teachers, parents, students, and the broader community to create shared understanding around digital literacy and online safety.

Implementation tips:

- Strengthen collaborations with parent associations, pediatricians, and community organizations to create comprehensive support networks.
- Transform traditional school authority structures by promoting collaborative, creative spaces that connect all educational stakeholders as co-learners and co-creators.
- Invite external experts and practitioners to bring specialized knowledge and real-world experience into school environments.

ASAP KEY RECOMMENDATIONS

FOR FAMILIES

FOR FAMILIES

1. FOSTERING OF OPEN AND NON-JUDGMENTAL DIALOGUE

Recommendation:

Cultivate regular dialogue with your children about their digital experiences through informal conversations that demonstrate genuine curiosity rather than surveillance or control.

Implementation tips:

- Position yourself as a co-learner rather than an authority figure – this will help build trust and mutual respect
- Practice active listening that validates children's experiences and perspectives, even when disagreeing with their choices
- Approach conflicts as learning opportunities rather than power struggles, focusing on understanding underlying needs and finding solutions that work for and satisfy both sides
- Create safe channels for children to report uncomfortable or harmful online experiences without fear of punishment

2. RESPONSIBLE DIGITAL BEHAVIORS PORTRAYAL

Recommendation:

Question your own behavioral models and digital habits, recognizing that pre-adolescents mirror behaviours and learn not only from what they observe but also from what they're told. Portray balanced technology use and digital mindfulness in your daily interactions with them.

Implementation tips:

- Consciously limit phone and device use during family time and direct interactions with pre-adolescents
- Practice intentional technology use by explaining when and why you use devices for specific purposes
- Acknowledge your own digital challenges, discussing struggles with screen time and digital distractions with your children
- Show that managing technology use is an ongoing challenge that requires continuous self-reflection and adjustment – even for you.

3. ADOPTION OF FAMILY DIGITAL AGREEMENTS

Recommendation:

Collaboratively develop a family digital agreement, ensuring all family members have input into rules and expectations. The agreement should reflect shared values rather than imposed restrictions.

Implementation tips:

- Implement "The habits I want to change" framework where all family members identify digital habits they wish to modify, promoting self-reflection and personal responsibility
- Involve children in defining screen time rules rather than imposing strict bans - prohibition can increase temptation
- Align home technology rules with your children's school policies and work with other families to ensure consistent implementation
- Involve other family members (e.g. grandparents) in the digital agreements – cooperation is fundamental for agreements to work out

4. IMPROVEMENT OF DIGITAL LITERACY COMPETENCIES

Recommendation:

Develop a comprehensive understanding of technology's basic principles and fundamental digital competencies to better guide and supervise your children's digital activities. Learning as a family is an important first step.

Implementation tips:

- Learn basic digital skills including password management, privacy settings, and online risk recognition
- Stay informed about the social media platforms, games, and applications your children use regularly
- Attend school digital literacy programs and workshops to support both your learning and school efforts
- Participate actively in parent-teacher discussions about digital challenges rather than simply receiving notifications about digital-related topics
- Be cautious of information overload and self-titled experts who offer simplistic solutions to complex digital challenges. Focus on evidence-based resources and professional guidance.

FOR FAMILIES

5. UNDERSTANDING DIGITAL DEPENDENCY AND SELF-REGULATION AS PRESSING TOPICS

Recommendation:

Learn to recognize signs of digital dependency and implement strategies to prevent and support healthy self-regulation skills.

Implementation tips:

- Monitor for inability to self-regulate screen time, decreased attention spans, and difficulty transitioning away from devices
- Create device-free zones within your home and establish routines that support both digital and offline activities, ensuring children have opportunities for diverse experiences and relationships
- Provide regular opportunities for activities requiring extended focus such as reading, puzzles, or in-depth conversations – and actively engage in them
- External controls are not enough – help your children build internal motivation and self-regulation

6. TEACHING CRITICAL INFORMATION EVALUATION

Recommendation:

Develop your child's ability to verify online information accuracy and recognize potential manipulation.

Implementation tips:

- Make information verification a routine family activity - consistently reminding children to check if online information is accurate will help them become conscientious of harmful information they might encounter online
- Use real examples from their online experiences as teaching opportunities to demonstrate fact-checking methods
- Show how to evaluate website credibility, check author credentials, and identify reliable versus unreliable sources
- Address dis- and misinformation in age-appropriate ways, explaining how false information spreads and why verification is essential

7. NAVIGATING SOCIAL MEDIA INFLUENCE AND PEER PRESSURE

Recommendation:

Help your children understand how digital platforms can affect social relationships, self-worth, and consumer behavior. Information is the best prevention possible.

Implementation tips:

- Discuss how social media access has become tied to social status and help children understand that their worth extends beyond digital platforms
- Teach recognition influencer marketing, using specific and familiar examples
- Address fear of missing out (FOMO) and social comparison by explaining how online presentations don't reflect complete reality
- Create alternative sources of social connection through in-person activities, such as participating in clubs, sports, and interests independent of digital platforms

8. EMOTIONAL AND SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT

Recommendation:

Develop essential soft skills for building strong, trustworthy relationships with your children, including empathetic listening, constructive conflict resolution, and collaborative negotiation techniques

Implementation tips:

- Prioritize face-to-face social interaction while teaching empathy and emotional regulation in digital contexts
- Explicitly discuss how digital communication impacts others' feelings and teach consideration and respect for the person behind every screen interaction
- Monitor for changes in emotional regulation, sleep patterns, or social behavior that might relate to digital (mis)use

FOR FAMILIES

9. MAINTAINING A BALANCED PERSPECTIVE ON DIGITAL ENGAGEMENT

Recommendation:

Recognize the positive aspects of children's digital engagement while maintaining awareness of potential risks, avoiding fear-based approaches that dismiss the value of online experiences.

Implementation tips:

- Acknowledge that digital spaces are real social environments where pre-adolescents build meaningful relationships and develop social skills
- Avoid oversimplified approaches (e.g. merely "reducing screen time") without understanding the context, purpose, or value of your child's digital activities.
- Support children in developing critical thinking skills about digital media and online relationships rather than imposing decisions
- Create family routines and spaces that support both digital and offline activities, ensuring diverse experiences and relationships

10. IMPLEMENTATION OF EFFECTIVE MONITORING AND GUIDANCE

Recommendation:

Combine appropriate oversight with educational conversations to promote digital literacy and self-awareness.

Implementation tips:

- Focus on building internal motivation and self-regulation rather than external controls – this can help children develop the skills they need to make healthy choices independently
- Avoid blaming children exclusively for device use issues; examine family patterns, environmental factors, and systemic contributions to digital behaviors

ASAP KEY RECOMMENDATIONS

FOR STAKEHOLDERS & POLICYMAKERS

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1. ESTABLISHMENT OF NATIONAL DIGITAL EDUCATION POLICY FRAMEWORKS

Recommendation:

Establish unified, coherent national policies that align digitalization efforts with educational goals while resolving contradictory directives about technology use in educational settings.

Implementation tips:

- Develop clear policy frameworks that provide consistent direction to schools, teachers, and parents about technology's role in education
- Address conflicts between policies promoting digital literacy and those restricting device access through approaches that maximize benefits while minimizing risks
- Create adaptable guidance frameworks that balance clear principles with flexibility for local adaptation to community needs and contexts
- Establish formal mechanisms for ongoing consultation with educators, parents, children, digital literacy experts, and community organizations

2. COMPREHENSIVE CURRICULUM STANDARDS AND INTEGRATION

Recommendation:

Mandate integration of critical digital literacy themes into national curricula, establishing progressive learning objectives that begin in primary education rather than in later educational levels.

Implementation tips:

- Create detailed, age-appropriate digital literacy standards for each grade level that build from basic digital operations to advanced critical thinking skills
- Focus on developing critical competencies rather than merely technical skills, emphasizing media literacy, ethical reasoning, privacy awareness, and critical evaluation of digital information
- Balance technical skills with digital citizenship education, requiring equal emphasis on technical competency and ethical digital behavior
- Support initiatives that address socioemotional and metacognitive aspects of digital media use, integrating social-emotional learning with digital education

FOR STAKEHOLDERS & POLICYMAKERS

3. PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT AND EDUCATOR SUPPORT

Recommendation:

Provide adequate, sustained funding and comprehensive support for educator training, including ongoing professional development and collaborative networks.

Implementation tips:

- Establish digital literacy as a compulsory subject in initial teacher training courses
- Allocate resources for regular teacher professional development in digital literacy education to address varying skill levels and rapid technology evolution
- Create specialist digital literacy educator roles and coordinators in schools and districts
- Fund platforms and programs that enable teachers to share best practices through formal collaboration networks
- Establish educator support networks that connect institutions to share innovative approaches, challenges, and solutions
- Ensure involvement of meaningful external experts to provide training, research insights, and evidence-based guidance

4. PARENT AND COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT

Recommendation:

Establish free parent education programs and community digital literacy centers to address the gap between children's advanced technology use and parents' digital knowledge.

Implementation tips:

- Require or encourage parent digital literacy programs as part of school enrollment processes
- Fund community digital literacy centers that provide accessible adult and family education opportunities
- Create family digital wellness initiatives that support healthy technology use patterns
- Foster partnerships between schools, families, community organizations, and technology companies
- Promote cooperation and shared responsibilities among all stakeholders while ensuring meaningful participation in policy development

FOR STAKEHOLDERS & POLICYMAKERS

5. EQUITY, ACCESS, AND CULTURAL RESPONSIVENESS

Recommendation:

Implement comprehensive programs that address disparities in technology access and digital skills while ensuring cultural responsiveness and multilingual support.

Implementation tips:

- Ensure universal access to technology and training, addressing situations where some families lack basic computer access while others provide unrestricted device access
- Develop tailored solutions that acknowledge diversity in socioeconomic contexts, cultural backgrounds, technological access, and learning needs
- Provide multilingual and culturally responsive resources that serve diverse communities effectively
- Support schools in under-resourced communities with additional funding and specialized programs
- Ensure resource accessibility across different languages, cultural contexts, and technological capabilities

6. SAFETY, RISK PREVENTION, AND PLATFORM ACCOUNTABILITY

Recommendation:

Enact comprehensive regulations establishing evidence-based guidelines for responsible digital media use while mandating platform accountability and transparency.

Implementation tips:

- Establish comprehensive online safety standards with detailed protocols for prevention, reporting, and response to harmful content exposure
- Regulate age-appropriate access in educational contexts through research-based guidelines and content filtering
- Mandate that social media and technology companies establish formal legal and operational presence within national jurisdictions
- Establish independent Social Media Authorities with adequate resources to regulate platform activities and ensure compliance with child protection standards
- Develop rigorous digital safety standards prioritizing user wellbeing over engagement metrics and profit maximization
- Implement transparency requirements enabling researchers and educators to understand platform impacts on young users

FOR STAKEHOLDERS & POLICYMAKERS

7. ASSESSMENT AND QUALITY ASSURANCE

Recommendation:

Mandate regular assessment of students' digital citizenship skills alongside technical competencies, ensuring measurable outcomes for ethical behavior and critical thinking.

Implementation tips:

- Create assessment frameworks that evaluate both technical skills and digital citizenship competencies
- Establish data collection systems to monitor student digital behavior, social-emotional development, and academic outcomes
- Develop feedback mechanisms allowing stakeholders to report implementation challenges and successes
- Ensure policies remain responsive to real-world conditions through continuous monitoring and evaluation

8. RESEARCH, EVIDENCE, AND PUBLIC AWARENESS

Recommendation:

Fund longitudinal research on digital education effectiveness while promoting evidence-based public awareness campaigns that counter misconceptions and moral panics.

Implementation tips:

- Invest in comprehensive research tracking long-term outcomes of different digital literacy approaches
- Build evidence base for policy decisions through systematic data collection and analysis
- Promote evidence-based public awareness campaigns that address myths and misconceptions about digital media use
- Provide families and communities with accurate, research-informed information for decision-making
- Counter oversimplified narratives about technology by acknowledging both opportunities and challenges

FOR STAKEHOLDERS & POLICYMAKERS

9. MULTI-STAKEHOLDER COLLABORATION AND GOVERNANCE

Recommendation:

Create Digital Education Advisory Councils and facilitate public-private partnerships while ensuring meaningful participation of all stakeholders, particularly children's voices.

Implementation tips:

- Establish councils including educators, parents, students, technology experts, and child development specialists
- Develop frameworks for collaboration with technology companies while maintaining public oversight of educational goals
- Ensure meaningful participation of children and young people in policy development processes
- Support international collaboration and learning through participation in global networks focused on digital education and child online safety
- Create formal processes for regularly updating digital education policies based on emerging research and technological changes

10. SUSTAINABILITY AND CONTINUOUS IMPROVEMENT

Recommendation:

Ensure long-term sustainability of digital literacy initiatives through adequate funding, institutional commitment, and continuous adaptation to technological and social changes.

Implementation tips:

- Establish regular policy review and update mechanisms that respond to rapid technological change
- Build adaptive policy frameworks capable of addressing new challenges and opportunities
- Ensure sustained funding for all digital literacy initiatives and support systems
- Create institutional structures that support continuous professional development and program evolution
- Develop and disseminate comprehensive, free, and open-access resources including digital literacy toolboxes for parents, pedagogical materials for teachers, and age-appropriate student resource

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